

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Ethane Diol by Os(VIII)

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The oxidation of ethane diol and 2-methoxy ethanol was studied by following the reaction colorimetrically. The reaction is alkali catalysed and the rate of reaction follows first order kinetics with respect to oxidant and diol. The reaction scheme suggesting open Os(VIII)-diol complex as an intermediate has been proposed.

OSMIUM(VIII) has been used as a catalyst in the reaction of many organic^{1,2} and inorganic^{3,4} compounds with different oxidising agents. Os(VIII) has been used as an independent oxidant for anthracene⁵, alcohol⁶, ascorbic acid⁷, sodiumtetrahydroborate⁸, phorbol⁹ and hydroxy acids^{10,11}. In view of the facts that 1,2-diols are easily cleaved under mild conditions, it was thought worthwhile to study their oxidation. The oxidation of ethane diol (ED) and 2-methoxy ethanol (2ME) was studied. The present report deals with the results on the kinetics of the oxidation of ethane diol by Os(VIII).

Experimental

Materials and methods :

OsO₄ (Johnson and Matthey) and ethane diol (B D H.) were used. All other chemicals were of A. R. grade. The solution of oxidant was prepared by dissolving one gram of OsO₄ in 393.4 ml of KOH solution (0.05 M).

The osmate ion absorbs strongly in the visible region, the kinetics of the reaction were followed colorimetrically using a Klett-Summerson photoelectric colorimeter employing filter no 42. The reaction was started by mixing a known volume of oxidant with requisite quantities of ED and NaOH, maintained at constant temperature ± 0.1°.

Stoichiometry :

The reaction mixtures with excess of Os(VIII) over reductant were thermostated at 35 ± 0.1° for 24 hours and analysed thereafter for unconsumed Os(VIII) content. One mole of ethane diol consumed three moles of Os(VIII).

Results and Discussion

The reaction shows first order dependence on Os(VIII) (Table 1) and [ED] (Table 2). Alkali has catalysing effect (Table 2). Increase in [H⁺] decreases

the rate of reaction (Table 2). The change in ionic strength by adding K₂SO₄ or KNO₃ shows no effect on rate constants (Table 3). Variation of rate with temperature is given in Table 4.

Acrylonitrile being immiscible, acrylamide was added to the reaction mixture and the rate was found to be unaffected. The observation that oxidation involves a two electron change and added olefinic monomer does not polymerise, excludes the possibility of free radical mechanism. OsO₄ in alkaline solution exists as an osmate ion^{1,2}, it is proposed that open osmate-diols complex (I) is the probable reaction intermediate, which subsequently decomposes into products.

TABLE 1 VARIATION OF RATE WITH [OXIDANT]
[ED] = 384 × 10⁻² M; [OH⁻] = 3.84 × 10⁻³ M; Temp. 35°

[Os(VIII)] × 10 ³ M	k _{obs} × 10 ³ sec ⁻¹
1.53	0.28
2.30	0.30
3.07	0.31
3.84	0.32
4.61	0.33

TABLE 2— VARIATION OF RATE WITH [ED], [OH⁻] AND [H⁺]

[Os(VIII)]=3.84 × 10 ⁻³ M; Temp. 35°					
[ED] × 10 ³ M	k _{obs} × 10 ³ sec ⁻¹	[OH ⁻] × 10 ³ M	k _{obs} × 10 ³ sec ⁻¹	[H ⁺]* × 10 ³ M	k _{obs} × 10 ³ sec ⁻¹
2.30	0.20	3.84	0.32	0.48	0.26
3.07	0.26	8.64	0.35	1.92	0.22
3.84	0.32	13.4	0.44	2.88	0.18
9.61	0.71	18.2	0.45	3.84	0.17
19.2	1.41	23.0	0.47	4.80	0.16
28.8	1.62	42.2	0.62	5.76	0.10
38.4	2.11	67.3	0.67		
57.6	2.55	115.3	0.83		

[OH⁻]* = 3.84 × 10⁻³ M [ED]* = 3.84 × 10⁻³ M
 [OH⁻]* = 3.84 × 10⁻³ M
 [SO₄²⁻]* = 5.77 × 10⁻³ M

TABLE 3— VARIATION OF RATE WITH IONIC STRENGTH

[Os(VIII)]=3.84 × 10 ⁻³ M; [ED]=3.84 × 10 ⁻³ M; [OH ⁻]=3.84 × 10 ⁻³ M; Temp. 35°		
μ × 10 ³ M	KNO ₃ k _{obs} × 10 ³ sec ⁻¹	K ₂ SO ₄ k _{obs} × 10 ³ sec ⁻¹
42.4	0.32	0.32
61.4	0.32	0.33
80.6	0.33	0.32
99.8	0.31	0.31
119.0	0.32	0.32

TABLE 4— VARIATION OF RATE WITH TEMPERATURE

[Os(VIII)]=3.84 × 10 ⁻³ M; [ED]=3.84 × 10 ⁻³ M [OH ⁻]=3.84 × 10 ⁻³ M	
Temp °C	k _{obs} × 10 ³ sec ⁻¹
30	0.19
35	0.32
40	0.52
45	0.72
50	1.01

The mechanistic step 2 suggesting formation of OsO₂(OH)₂²⁻ species is in agreement with the fact that Os(VI) conclusively exists as OsO₂(OH)₂²⁻.^{1,3}

2ME and ED show identical kinetic behaviour and comparable rates of oxidation (Table 5), since 2ME cannot form a cyclic complex, the extension of the same analogy to ED, suggests that probably oxidation of ED takes place through the formation of an open

TABLE 5— COMPARATIVE RATE CONSTANTS

[Os(VIII)]=3.84 × 10 ⁻³ M; [Reductant]=3.84 × 10 ⁻³ M; [OH ⁻]=3.84 × 10 ⁻³ M; Temp. 35°		
	ED	2ME
k _{obs} × 10 ³ sec ⁻¹	0.32	0.18
K _{eq} l. mole ⁻¹	1.84	2.49
k × 10 ³ sec ⁻¹	5.00	2.00

complex I. The sequence of Eq. (1) and (2) leads to the following rate law

$$-\frac{d \text{Os(VIII)}}{dt} = \frac{k K_{eq} [\text{ED}] [\text{OsO}_2]}{1 + K_{eq} [\text{ED}]} \quad \dots (3)$$

Rate law (3) explains the order with respect to [Oxidant] and [ED].

OsO₄(OH)₂²⁻ is the reactive oxidant species, higher alkali concentration should increase the concentration of OsO₄(OH)₂²⁻ species displacing eqn (1) to the right.

At $[\text{OH}^-] > 3.84 \times 10^{-3} M$, alkali catalyses the reaction (Table 2), but the alkali has been found to be less effective catalyst than would have been predicted by eqn. $\text{OsO}_4 + 2\text{OH}^- \rightleftharpoons \text{OsO}_4(\text{OH})_2^{2-}$. It seems that alkali catalyses the formation of an intermediate complex.

Plot of $1/k_{obs}$ versus $1/[\text{ED}]$ was linear with the positive intercept, lending support to the formation of an osmate-diol complex, in agreement with the proposed mechanism. The values of k and $K_{s,q}$ calculated from intercept and slope were found to be $5.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ sec}^{-1}$ and $1.84 \text{ l. mole}^{-1}$ respectively.

The activation parameters ΔE , PZ and ΔS^\ddagger were evaluated and found to be 16.35 Kcals, $2.06 \times 10^9 \text{ sec}^{-1}$, -16.80 E. U. respectively.

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